

Teachers' Perceptions Regarding Retirement In Gauteng Schools

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 01,2023</p> <p>Accepted: November 01,2023</p> <p>Keywords : Teachers, Pre-Retirement, Preparedness, Gauteng Schools</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10059910</p>	<p><i>In this study the focus is on the exploration and description of the teachers' perceptions regarding retirement in Gauteng schools. From the individual and group interviews, the findings are leading to suggestions that a more comprehensive programme for preparing teachers for retirement is highly necessary. All the participants were aware of their retirement age of 60 years as stipulated in the department of education internal memorandum No: 05 of 2021, which states that the compulsory retirement age in the public service is 60 years. It further states that the age restriction is in accordance with Chapter 4 of the Public Service Act, 1994 and Chapter 4 of the Employment of Educators Act, 1998, as amended.</i></p> <p><i>it came out that there are some anxieties and fears as the majority seemed not ready and maybe not prepared enough for the retirement. Recommendations for a pre-retirement programme aimed at timeous preparation which may include, psychological, financial and ability to keep functioning post retirement will be proposed to the department of education in Gauteng and for the Tshwane North district as the pilot site on approval.</i></p>

Introduction

There are several studies conducted on retirements planning and some are retirement planning and behaviours of middle and high income earners in South Africa by Kajauchire (2015). the knowledge of and involvement in retirement planning among employees in their middle adulthood by Mushaphi, (2010), needs assessment for a pre-retirement programme in the South African Police Services by Diko, (2013). These studies did not look at teachers' perceptions regarding their retirement in Gauteng schools, and the findings on this study will add to the body of work in the retirement space.

The Government Pensions Employees Fund (GEPF) administers the Teachers pensions and it is Africa's largest pension fund. The fund has more than 1.2 million active members and approximately 300 000 pensioners and beneficiaries The Department of Education is one of the largest GEPF member departments (GEPF, 2020). In its mission to satisfy its members, the GEPF is continuously enhancing its communication efforts to meet the needs of their external and internal stakeholder.

Throughout the study the researcher was guided by the research question and the formulated aim of the study as follows:

Research question

Research question can be explained as that which give a researcher direction in his/her the study. Based on the above, the research question can thus be formulated in this study as:

- What are teachers' perceptions regarding retirement in Gauteng schools?

Research aim

From the above research question, the aim of the study is thus derived and is formulated as follows:

- to explore and describe teachers' perceptions regarding retirement in Gauteng schools

From the results of the study, it came out that the teachers in the Gauteng Department of Education, Tshwane District have a mix of high perceptions and low in relation to readiness. The positive high perception might be influenced by the perception on the contributory pension scheme which makes savings retirement compulsory for all teachers and the fact that they will have money. This was coming out in some of the responses that referred to "I will now enjoy my money".

Although some teachers feel very uncomfortable when getting closer to retirement age because of the hardship occasioned by not feeling ready to handle the amount of money and not feeling prepared for the life post retirement. Some even indicated that they are still fit to can continue with some work, assisting in the education value chain for the benefit of learners, newly appointed teachers and the Department.

It is imperative that the teachers have the product knowledge as far as their pension fund and the ability to meet life goals through the proper management of finances with the right saving attitudes (Wilson & Aggrey, 2012). Life goals which usually involve necessities of life, can include buying a home. This may also include decisions whether one is able to work post retirement because there are institutions that are looking for experienced teachers who still can work with extensive skills on a short term or part time basis. According to Fitzpatrick (2018) labor force participation rates of college-educated women ages 60 to 64 increased by 20% between 2000

and 2010. Not everyone want to or can afford to quit working after retiring from a full time career in education. If one still expects to work part time, think about how that income might influence how much one need to save and how much investment risk to consider. That being said it is not always possible to work when we are older, we might have to take care of our aging parents or find that our own health is not allowing. With all this it probably seems like there is less advice on the available options, hence it is critical for the Gauteng Department of Education to invest on the pre-retirement planning and readiness for teachers so as to maximise that quality of life post retirement. Ettema (2011) argues that teacher pensions are fast becoming a key issue in education policy.

The quality of life during retirement takes into consideration activities that keeps one functioning. The category of networking and engagements relates to relationship connectedness to a person's job or environment. Purposeful living activities that keeps one looking forward to more days doing something that brings meaning to person's life.

The trend around the world is that people are living longer and life expectancy is increasing. In South Africa, (Stats SA, 2015) it is reported that life expectancy at birth is estimated at 61 years, having increased from an estimated 52 years in 2005. The latest for 2019 is estimated at 61, 5 for males and 67, 7 for females. With the increase in life expectancy, there are implications for the economy as people live far longer than in previous decades and consequently needs significantly more in terms of retirement savings. However, the opposite is true as a large proportion of individuals are claimed not to plan for retirement or their life expectancy into account.

Theoretical Framework

This research study is based on the teachers' perceptions regarding retirement in Gauteng schools. The theoretical framework used in this study is In line with the illustration in figure 1, it can be summarised that the life course perspective can be applied widely to readiness and preparedness through a life span starting from prenatal to the retirement age of teachers. In addition, the LCP was also applied in longitudinal studies such studies of childhood development, middle years, and later lives (Elder et al. 2015). This included the recognition that individual lives are influenced by their ever-changing historical contexts including retirement

Figure 1. Broad themes of the life course perspective

According to this theoretical framework, preparedness start at an early ages of life the school which represent the place of work in which teacher becomes part of the wider society and viewed as a system linked to the wider society which are in constant dynamic interdependent relationship. Accumulation of the positive or negative health and well-being during the life span will have an impact during the retirement period. The entire system in the life course is meant to prepare for future state like when one is outside the actively full-time employment and gained the status of a retiree. Being ready and prepared for older ages emotionally, financially and a positive health status is almost equal healthy retirement period. Ill preparedness may continue to perpetuate the inequities in the system from generation to generation. In this context, this means that what happens in one part can affect the other parts at a macro level. Based on the above explanation, this research views teachers'

retirement as an important point that needs to be intensively researched on to further empower, prepare and contribute to sustainable livelihood in older ages, outside the full time employment.

This study attempted to describe all the aspects that take place before teachers exit from their full-time employment. It was important to understand how retirement preparation happens in the Gauteng Department of Education. According to Patricia et al (2018), retiring is a lifelong process that is socially constructed at different stages as detailed by Elder (2015) in the life course perspective theoretical framework (life span, timing and place). Through the individual and group interviews, the 18 sampled teachers expressed their opinions, the meaning and understanding of how teachers are supported during retirement preparations in the Tshwane North district of Gauteng Department of Education.

Collection and analysis of data

According to Flick (2015), sampling refers to strategies that ensure the researcher has the ‘right’ cases for the specific study. Sampling is an important aspect of the research design. It involves selecting a population (a group of individuals) that is suitable for the research study and its objectives. The intent is to find individuals who are best suited to provide significant data about the phenomenon (Minchiello & Kottler, 2010). Flick (2015) further stated that researchers select participants purposively in small numbers according to how relevant they are and that it does not only deal with finding participants but also with finding sites where the participants can be found. The sample size was the total of 18 teachers considered the diversity of teachers in age, backgrounds and mixed male and female. The selection from rural and urban schools was adequate to provide manageable set of data that answered the research question.

Although the proposal and chapter one stated that the study would be conducted in three school, the researcher was given the opportunity to select more than three schools (urban and rural) for the purpose of establishing much deeper experience. The selected schools were in the Gauteng Department of Education, Tshwane North District

Considerations

Considering the COVID-19 period and its challenges, the hybrid of individual (in person and online) were explored. The focus group interviews were scheduled on the schools’ premises and were arranged by the principals. Each situation was approached on the feasibility in line with the back to work protocols and health and safety requirements as detailed in circular 18 of 2020 of the department of Public Service and Administration (DPSA).

Transferability

Transferability refers to the outcomes of the research to be applied to similar situations (du Plooy-Cilliers, 2017). Although the study is confined to the three schools in of the Tshwane North district of the Gauteng Department of Education, the study could be done in other districts of the Gauteng Department and across National and Local Departments.

Literature on teachers’ perception regarding retirement in Gauteng schools

According to Matemane (2018) there is lack of preparedness and planning for the life outside the full-time employment – in this case teachers. This means that a number of employees (teachers) who have worked for many years, when they retire, they cannot continue to sustain the quality of lives or life standard post retirement. This phenomenon is experienced around many families and social circles. According to Kajauchire (2015), Matemane (2018), and Struwig et.al (2013) who looked at saving before retirement, found that only 48% for example of African Blacks are in favour of financial planning and household’s budgets. This is supported by the participants responses that not much is done on the preparedness and hence the anxieties and frustrations and thus answers the research question on the perception of teachers regarding retirement.

Recommendations

For the Department of Education management, the knowledge will assist within districts on the formulation of the retirement Education and the pre-retirement counselling for all the would-be retiree teachers. The programme will assist in inspiring a life worth living post retirement. Teachers may look forward to life of worth because they would have planned well and ready for the time outside their formal employment. By considering the implementation of a pre-retirement programme the Department would ease the sense of despair, shame, tears and retirement will not be sorrowful and frustrating. The following will be recommended:

Pre-retirement Education programme

1. Counselling programme in various aspects of retirement adjustments.
2. Financial management
3. Health and Wellness management
4. GEPP awareness about the scheme and its benefits

Conclusion

Lifelong learning and life preparedness for all eventuality is not a luxury. Workshops and information sessions that may impart knowledge of the retirement benefits and how to plan better for the retirement may increase the comfort during the retirement period. Programmes that may be considered shall be holistic in nature and addresses the well-being and post retirement options to keep functional. Some teachers as revealed during data collection, retire still in good health and willing to contribute to the department in different ways. The programmes must include such opportunities and all requirements to access such should a potential retiree wish to explore.

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